

How to create a semantically interlinked Cultural Heritage Knowledge Graph from heterogeneous distributed repositories?

Examples from CH Artefacts, Holy Wells and Cultural Heritage covered with Campanian Ignimbrite tephra

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Session: RDM in an agile world of Knowledge Hubs

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In the interdisciplinary field of Cultural Heritage, research data is dispersed across heterogeneous and distributed repositories

label — **Phaistos disc** (Q465338)

description — inscribed tablet found in Crete
Phaistos Disk | Phaestos Disc
▶ [In more languages](#)

Statements

property — **inception** — **value** — **1700 BCE**

earliest date	1700 BCE
latest date	1100 BCE
sourcing circumstances	circa
reason for preferred rank	preferred determination method

qualifiers

rank — **▼ 1 reference**

stated in	Le pouvoir de l'écrit
author	Louis Godart
page(s)	206

opened reference

statement group

rank — **▼ 1400 BCE**

end time	1970
start time	1959

collapsed reference

property — **location of discovery** — **value** — **Phaistos**

statement group

▶ 0 references

+ add reference
+ add value
+ add (statement)

item identifier — (Q465338)

aliases —

Mtrognitz, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Integrating community-driven infrastructures such as the Wikiverse and OpenStreetMap supports also AI systems

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Building semantically interlinked and federated Knowledge Graphs relay on community standards, such as the CIDOC-CRM, terminologies, and Linked Open Data (LOD) technologies

FAIR access to Cultural Heritage data plays a crucial role in fostering transparency, reproducibility, and community engagement

The urgency of these efforts becomes evident when considering how cultural heritage continues to shape contemporary society

Example: The Ogham Stone CIIC 506 (GIGHA/1) on the Isle of Gigha

By **Katherine Forsyth**, OG(H)AM UK Principal Investigator

Any of you participating in the 'Dry January' challenge will, I hope, forgive this month's featured ogham. It comes courtesy of a microbrewery on the Isle of Gigha which declares itself 'dedicated to crafting unique, small-batch beers that capture the essence of this stunning Hebridean island. ... every pint is a love letter to this special place.' That letter is written in the ogham alphabet, of course!

Gigha Brewery are proud of the island's wonderful ogham pillar which we were delighted to visit and record back in 2022 when we acquired these bottles – for purely scientific purposes 🧐. There is a separate section on their [website](#) dedicated to ogham – the only brewery in the world to be so distinguished – and the script also features on their product labels. Ogham is not so easy on a smooth, round bottle (though there are ways!), and they employ a drawn-in stem-line, but the script is otherwise classic. They even use the first forid (X) in its oldest value: /k/ to represent the first letter of their top-brewed 'Kölsch'-style beer.

As you can see, the ogham is used to represent the English names of their beers and, as often happens with modern use of ogham mediated via the Web, the letters are rather widely spaced. They could all be slightly closer together, especially in G-O-L-D-E-N A-L-E where there are no two successive letters from the same *aicme* (group). So, there is no room for confusion – exactly as the script was planned to ensure.

Og(h)am of the Month Jan 2025: S-ARL-001 (CIIC 506 | GIGHA/1)

Ogham as part of the local heritage and brewery identity

This tells us that **Lait(h)** = Ale, the stuff consumed copiously in Northern society at this season, plus **Irt** = killed.

So **Latheirt** means “ale-killed”, ale has killed us.

The rather unimaginative translator adds that the Latin meaning is **crapula**, or “drunkenness”

– Roger Pearse

O'D guesses 'a threadbare cloak': but cf. W. *Humman* 'a banner'. O'Clery has *lomain* i. *brat* 'mantle'.—Ed.

LATHERT ['drunkenness'] i.e. *lait(h)* 'ale' and *irt* 'death' to him who drank it: [*var. lectio*] i.e. the drinking of beer or ale killed him. *lathert* (gl. c)rapula) *Ir. Glosses*, No. 286. *lait(h)* = Corn. *lad* (gl. liquor), *Lat. latex*.—Ed.

LUOBORT ('a herb-garden') melius est (i.e. *lath-gort* i.e. *gort lath* 'a garden of vegetables').

lathgort *Lib. Arm.* 17 b. 1: *lathgort* (gl. olitor) *Z.* 45. Corn. *luworth, lowarth, Br. liorz*—*lath* = AS. *leof*, Ogh. *lath*, and *gort* = *χρῶρον, hortus*. This gloss can hardly have been written in the tenth century.—Ed.

LÍN ('flax') a *lino*. *Léine* ('a shirt') a *linceo* one from another. Now *lios*, Manx *lioen*, W. and Bret. *lhin*.—Ed.

LÁNOMAIN ('a married couple') i. *lánshomáin* full property of each other, for each is half property without the other

B adds: Aliter *lanamain* quasi *lanamain* ('clinging') ar ni fil etarecard doib acht ar dia ('for there is no sundering of them save for God's sake'): *lánamain* 'matrimonium' *Z.* 988,989.—Ed. Manx *lannoon* 'a couple'.—Ed.

Ogham gloss that reads in Irish Latheirt, i.e. massive hangover.

Beer creates even this week new inscriptions of cultural experience

Example: Pattern of Sheestown at Saint Fiachra's Well

Master of Jean Rolin II, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Fiacre [Collapse]
 Irish saint

Sant Fiachra, pátrún na n-garraíodóirí

Upload media ↗

Wikipedia ↗

Date of birth 607 (statement with Gregorian date earlier than 1584) Ireland

Date of death 668 (statement with Gregorian date earlier than 1584) Meaux

Place of burial Meaux Cathedral

Country of citizenship Dál Riata

Authority control [Collapse]

Q953927

VIAF ID: 57743610 ↗

GND identifier: 131360958 ↗

Oxford Biography Index Number: 9378 ↗

Reasonator ↗ • Scholia ↗ • Wikidocumentaries ↗ • PelScan ↗ • statistics ↗ • WikiMap ↗ • Locator tool ↗ • KML file ↗ • Search depicted ↗

Saint Fiachra's Well [Collapse]
 holy well in the townland of Sheestown/Sheestown, Co. Kilkenny

Upload media ↗

Instance of Holy Well Semantic Concept

Concept holy well (2023, in use)

Named after Fiacre

Location County Kilkenny
 Kilferagh
 Ireland

Diocese Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory

Collection Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II Survey of Holy Wells County Kilkenny Phase 1 and Phase 2. A report prepared for Kilkenny County Council Heritage Office as an action of the Kilkenny Heritage Plan, 2024

Inventory number 166 (Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II) KH/ND44 (Survey of Holy Wells County Kilkenny Phase 1 and Phase 2. A report prepared for Kilkenny County Council Heritage Office as an action of the Kilkenny Heritage Plan, 2024)

Authority control [Collapse]

Q121842432

OpenStreetMap node ID: B515205450 ↗

Reasonator ↗ • Scholia ↗ • Wikidocumentaries ↗ • PelScan ↗ • statistics ↗ • WikiMap ↗ • Locator tool ↗ • KML file ↗ • WikishootMap ↗ • OpenStreetMap ↗ • Search depicted ↗

via <https://irelandsholywells.blogspot.com/2012/07/saint-fiachras-well-kilkenny.html>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Saint Fiachra's Well in Kilferagh, County Kilkenny, Ireland

Pattern of Sheestown (Q19035790)

Item: Discussion

Read View history

annual pattern at St Patrick's Well in Sheestown, Co. Kilkenny

Pattern of Sheestown | Sheestown Pattern | Sheestown Pattern | Pattern of St. Finian

in more languages

Statements

instance of	pattern	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

image		edit
	Bishop Cull at St. Pat's	
	3,028 × 2,000, 4.75 MB	
	0 references	

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

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Annual Pattern of Sheestown, County Kilkenny, Ireland

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

How to “feed” the (CH-) **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem?**

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

Irish Ogham Stones

Linked Ogham (RDF)
 Wikidata & other Wikibases
 FDO (3D Models & Software)
 OSM, TEI/EpiDoc

Holy Wells

Wikidata
 OSM & FDO (3D Models)

Campanian Ignimbrite

Linked Open Data (fuzzy-sl Ont.)
 fuzzy-sl Wikibase
 OpenStreetMap & Wikidata
 FDO (Research Software)

Govan Artefacts

Wikidata & Wikibases
 OSM & FDO (3D Models)

Four Use Cases from heterogeneous distributed repositories

Ogham Stones

Mix of all Sources ...

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

(C) OpenStreetMap contributors
Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ogham! 4.-6. AD, early Medieval, “Primitive Irish”

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

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wmde.org/opensciencefellows

Ogham Stones within the KG Ecosystem

Extract from the Linked Open Ogham Ontology

THE OGHAM AND ANALOGOUS INSCRIPTIONS OF SCOTLAND.¹

COUNTY OF ARGYLL.

506.—Gigha.

1899, *JRSAI* 29 : 345. 1901, *JRSAI* 31 : 18 (Rhys) 440 (Macalister). 1926, *Scottish Gaelic Studies* 1 : 3 (F. C. Diack).

On the top of a knoll overlooking the village, on the side of the island of Gigha facing the mainland : now protected by a wooden fence. (It is easily visible from the mainland when the spectator knows where to look for it). Slaty grit, 6' 8" × 0' 10" × 0' 8½". Inscription cut and rubbed on the

N.W. angle, and now worn and in very bad condition : the sides of the stone show frets of vertical and horizontal lines, which are evidently modern additions. The inscription reads :

VICULA MAQ CUGINI

The first C is not to be resolved into DD. The angle at 1U is broken, and this letter might be an O. The following letter is certainly L, though in some aspects of the stone it looks like S : L² and M run into one another. There is a hole 2½" across in the edge between the M and the following A, and in the opposite edge there is a similar hole corresponding to it : the first of these, at least, must have been on the stone before the inscription was cut, as the lapidary passed it over. A triangular flake has been broken away from the H-surface between the Q and 2C, but apparently without injuring the inscription. 2U is faint though traceable, but the final I can only be guessed at.

CIIC 506 Gigha Ogham Stone

GIGHA/1

Corpus Refs: [Macalister/1945:506](#)

Site: [GIGHA](#)

Discovery: first mentioned, 1873 White, T.P.

History: Forsyth/1996, 288: 'not until the latter half of the nineteenth [century] was any mention made of the ogham inscription [the stone itself having been known since the seventeenth century]. The first to submit the inscription to critical examination was a party from the Royal Society of Antiquaries of Ireland, who, on the recommendation of Rhys, included the stone in their 1899 archaeological tour of the Scottish Islands. ... The stone has fallen and been re-erected at least twice. The first recorded fall came in about 1843-4 when the stone was toppled 'by some young men for their own amusement'. The piece that broke off the top as a result of the incident was incorporated into a nearby pigsty, and subsequently into the masonry of new houses built on the site. ... After the fall, on the instructions of the landowner, the stone was dragged back to the top of the hillock and re-erected on its old site 'with great care'. It was fixed in place by a mason, but, because the hillock had been quarried on one side, towards the base of the stone, it fell again some twenty years later, i.e. c. 1864. According to local witnesses the condition of the stone was not impaired by the second fall. Rather than re-erect it precisely on the original site, the new owner ordered it be replaced 'at a very short distance'.

Geology: Forsyth/1996, 290: 'Granite'. Macalister/1945, 484: 'Slaty grit'.

Dimensions: 1.7 x 0.25 x 0.31 (Forsyth/1996)

Setting: in ground

Location: on site

Forsyth/1996, 28: 'Though this is not the original location of the stone, according to local tradition, it is very close to it'.

Form: plain

Forsyth/1996, 290: 'A tall, four-sided pillar'.

Condition: complete, poor

Forsyth/1996, 290: 'Poor...In addition to general weathering, there are a number of more specific injuries, most serious of which are unevenly spaced chunks missing from the ogham-bearing aris'.

Folklore: none

Crosses: none

Decorations: no other decoration

References

- [Fisher/2001](#) 117 photo concise discussion
- [Forsyth/1996](#) 288–291 photo concise discussion
- [Macalister/1945](#) 484 concise discussion

via https://linkedopenogham.github.io/cisp-recovery/cisp/database/stone/gigha_1.html

GIGHA/1/1

Readings

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): VICULAMAQ CUGINI

Explanation:

VICULA MAQ CUGINI

[Macalister/1945](#) 484 reading only

Forsyth, K.S. (1996): V[IC]U[L]A[M]A[Q]U[I][T]O[M]G[IL]U[I]E

Explanation:

V[IC]U[L]A MAQ[U]I [C]U[G]I[N]I

[Forsyth/1996](#) 291–298 substantial discussion

Notes

Orientation: vertical up

Position: inc ; aris ; inc ; undecorated

Inclusion: inc

Date: 600 – (RCAHMS/1971)

Jackson in RCAHMS/1971, 96: 'perhaps not older than the 7th century'.

400 – 599 (Forsyth/1996)

Forsyth/1996, 297, suggests that Jackson's date may be too late, arguing that 'the final vowels -i-u and -i may indeed be present and thus the text need not post-date apocope'.

Language: Goidelic (ogham)

Ling. Notes: Forsyth/1996, 291–297 persuasively argues for seeing this stone as the product of a goidelic milieu.

Paleography: Forsyth/1996, 295: 'Gigha is written in the classic ... Ogham with no drawn stem-line and vowels which are little more than nicks - the 'text-book' form of the script'.

Legibility: poor

Forsyth/1996, 292: 'The first six letters are extremely doubtful'.

Lines: 1

Carving errors: 0

Doubtful: no

Names

- [Vicula](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of [Macalister/1945](#), 484.
- [Cugini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of [Macalister/1945](#), 484.
- [Vicula](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of [Forsyth/1996](#), 296.
- [\[C\]h\[ae\]m\[ig\]i\[n\]i](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of [Forsyth/1996](#).

References

- [Fisher/2001](#) 117 photo concise discussion
- [Forsyth/1996](#) 291–297 photo substantial discussion
- [Macalister/1945](#) 484 drawing concise discussion
- [RCAHMS/1971](#) 96–97, Fig 107, Plate 16 photo, drawing substantial discussion

CIIC 506 Gigha Ogham Stone @ CISP Database

via <https://github.com/guariento/og-h-am/blob/main/XML/S-ARL/S-ARL-001.xml>

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  <idno type="CISP">GIGHA/1</idno>
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  </availability>
</publicationStmt>

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    <msIdentifier>
      <country>Scotland</country>
      <repository/>
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    </msIdentifier>
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      <msItem>
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      </msItem>
    </msContents>
    <physDesc>
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          <objectType key="monument">Pillar</objectType>
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            <width>0.25 at base, 0.20 at the top</width>
            <depth>0.31 at base, 0.23 at the top</depth>
          </dimensions>
        </supportDesc>
        <condition>A tall, square-shaped pillar, it <q>is unclear whether the monument is a re-used pre-historic standing stone or a pillar specially erected for the bearing of the inscription</q> (Forsyth 1996, 289). <q>The stone has fallen and been re-erected at least twice</q>; the first time it was intentionally toppled by some young men while the second fall was as a result of quarrying near the base on one side of the stone (ibid. 288-289). There is general weathering with <q>a series of four large, shallow, unevenly spaced chunks missing from the ogham-bearing arris</q> (ibid. 290). The ogham inscription <q>which is worn and in bad condition, is defaced by series of spalls on the arris</q> (ibid. 290). The portion of the inscription <q>nearest the ground is the most badly worn and the most disputed</q> (ibid. 291).
        </condition>
      </objectDesc>
      <layoutDesc>
        <layout style="vertical" rend="arris_up">The ogham inscription is on the north west edge of the four-sided pillar stone and reads upwards from the bottom.
      </layoutDesc>
      <objectDesc>
        <handDesc>
          <handNote>There is a wide range of published interpretations of the ogham that along with its general poor condition make a definitive reading difficult. On the same grounds, it is difficult to make definitive statements about its carving technique. <q>As they now survive, the strokes are finger-scale and with a U-section, where it can be measured with any certainty the length of h-acute strokes is about <math>40\text{--}60\text{mm}</math></q> (Forsyth 1996, 291). The gaps between the letters most likely contained vowel notches now lost. Forsyth (ibid. 295) describes the ogham inscription as <q>ogham with no drawn stem-line and vowels which are little more than nicks - the 'text-book' form of the script</q>.
        </handNote>
      </handDesc>
    </physDesc>
    <history>
      <origin>
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          <note>National Grid Reference: NR 6426 4817</note>
        </origPlace>
        <origDate>
        </origDate>
      </origin>
      <provenance type="found" when="1873">Formerly the middle stone of a straight alignment of three stones known locally as the 'Clocks of Gigha'. The ogham stone is located on a hillock, <placeName>Cnoc na Carraigh ('hill of the rock')</placeName>, about 90 m NW of the ruined chapel of Kilchattan on the island of <placeName>Gigha</placeName>. Although the stone has been noted since <date>1695</date>, the inscription was not noticed until <date>1873</date>.
      </provenance>
      <provenance type="observed" when="2022-09-14">Visited and recorded in situ in 2022.
      </provenance>
    </history>
  </msDesc>
</sourceDesc>
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E22

E25

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

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  </div>
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  <ab>
    <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"><gap reason="lost" quantity="6" unit="character"/><unclear cert="low">MA</unclear>Q<gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/>C</unclear cert="low">OGIN</unclear><gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="apparatus">
  <listApp>
    <app n="1">
      <note>As Forsyth notes <q>The first six letters are extremely doubtful</q>. For the portion of the inscription closest to the ground, the indentations of strokes <q>can be clearly felt on the arbris, but the lines are too indistinct to interpret</q> (1996, 292). From the seventh character onwards the carving is clearer and there is greater agreement amongst previous editors (ibid. 293).</note>
    </app>
    <app n="2">
      <note>Rhys (1899) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1899">
        MAQICAGILEB
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="3">
      <note>Rhys (1901, 18-23) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1901">
        OGMMA MAQI TIGERNI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="4">
      <note>Macalister (1902) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="MAC1902">
        VICULA MAQ COMGINI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="5">
      <note>Macalister (1945, 484) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="MAC1945">
        VICULA MAQ CUGINI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <!--<app n="6">
      <note>Diack (1926) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="DIACK1926">
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
        VIDDOSAMO QICOGINI
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    <!--<app n="7">
      <note>Jackson (1971, 96-97) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="JAC1971">
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
        H\-\JMAQT/cAGII/bb
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    </listApp>
  </div>
  <div type="translation">
    <p>According to Forsyth (1996, 297), Jackson offered <q>a very hypothetical</q> interpretation: the son of <persName>Coicéile</persName> (see <ref target="https://canmore.org.uk/event/695592">Canmore</ref>).</p>
  </div>
  <div type="commentary">
    <p><q>If the letters before the M are not admitted then the formula 'MAQ-X' is likely, either as 'the son of X', or more likely, as a compound name with first element MAQ (Forsyth 1996, 296)</q>. However, Forsyth maintains that there is sufficient evidence for the existence of some ogham carvings before the letter M which consequently implies that Gigha 1 conforms to the Irish formula 'X son of Y'.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 297) also rejects Macalister's suggestion for VICULA as <foreign xml:lang="sga">Fiacal</foreign> meaning 'tooth' on the grounds that <q>OIr ia is from earlier e, both long and short i remained as i</q>. Meanwhile the second name COMGINI is interpreted by Macalister as OIR <persName xml:lang="sga">Coemgen</persName>, which Forsyth comments is a <q>widespread and well-known male name (<foreign xml:lang="sga">Coemgen</foreign> + <foreign xml:lang="sga">gen</foreign> + <foreign xml:lang="sga">comgen</foreign> 'Fair born' (Uhllich 1993:2071)), found variously spelled, including <persName xml:lang="ga">Comganiz</persName></q>.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 296) is in favor of considering this example as one of the earliest oghams in Scotland due to the fact that comparable scripts are ubiquitous in Ireland. Moreover, the stone's size and shape, and the positioning of the inscriptions' lettering and proportion of its strokes which is, as she notes <q>closest of all the Scottish examples to the Southern Irish norm</q> (ibid., 297).
  </div>

```

TX1

TX6

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

CIIC 81

- UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4
- OSM Node: 11071361392
- Wikidata: Q130529871

Open Street Map Contributors, ODBL

© OpenStreetMap contributors, Imagery © Mapbox

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergeo

Änderungssatz #13909380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A7O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

- *Analogue Sources: CIIC, CISP*
- *Linked Open Ogham Data: providing the primary URI*
 - http://lod.ogham.link/data/OghamStone_Squirrel_collection
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase: coordinates and how they are created*
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD*
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakt Wikibase: 3D Model & Annotations*
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians: Inscription & Persons & Words*
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)
- *TEI/EpiDOC (from the OG(H)AM project)*
- *Open Street Map*
 - [historic=ogham_stone](#)

Use each Repository for data it is “famous” for ...

BARONY OF KINALEA**Upton (97).**

At Upton¹, near Inishannon, a stone scored with Ogham writing was found in taking down an old wall, in the year 1837. A promise was made to Windele that the stone would be sent to him, but the promise was never fulfilled, and he heard afterwards that it had been broken up for building purposes. There is no certain guarantee that this and the Lisconigill stone, of which a similar story is told, were any more Ogham than the Youghal stone just mentioned, which was found in similar circumstances.]

BARONY OF KINALMEAKY**81.—Garranes (84).**

1869 JRSAL 10 : 260 (Brash). 1911 * *Ivernian* 3 : 73 (Henebry).
On this townland there is an interesting group of earth-works which have recently been examined by excavation. The

C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUOICI CALLITI¹ There is no townland of this name in the locality.via https://linkedopenogham.github.io/cisp-recovery/cisp/database/stone/gares_1.html**GARES/1****Corpus Refs:** [Macalister/1945:81](#)**Site:** [GARES](#)**Discovery:** recognised, 1852 Crowley

History: Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: According to Brash, *JRSAL* 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the Rath in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P.O. [Reardon's](#) article in *PRIA* 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. -- According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in *JRSAL* 10, 1869). Macalister states in *CIIC* that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Garranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskilkeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868.

The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still 'standing loosely in one of the ditches': *CIIC* 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.

Geology: Macalister/1945, 84: 'clayslate'.**Dimensions:** 1.75 x 0.48 x 0.18 (converted from Macalister/1945)**Setting:** in ground**Location:** University College, Cork (Cat: 17)

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still 'standing loosely in one of the ditches': *CIIC* 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.

Form: plain

Condition: complete ; some
Macalister/1945, 84: 'a little chipped'.

Folklore: none**Crosses:** none**Decorations:** no other decoration**References**

- [Gippert/Web](#) Ogham 81 photo, drawing substantial discussion [[Gippert 81](#)]
- [Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 photo, drawing concise discussion

GARES/1/1**Readings**Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): [C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]SMAQI](#) || |IMUC || |C[O]CALLITI**Expansion:**[C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]S MAQI MUOICI CALLITI](#)[Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 reading only[Zieglert/1981](#) 145-146, 258 reading onlyGippert, J. (1987): [C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]SMAQI](#) || |IMUC || |C[O]CALLITI**Expansion:**[C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]S MAQI MUOICI CALLITI](#)[Gippert/1985](#) Ogham 81 reading only [[Gippert 81](#)]McManus, D. (1991): [C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]SMAQI](#) || |IMUC || |C[O]CALLITI**Expansion:**[C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]S MAQI MUOICI CALLITI](#)[McManus/1991](#) 93-94[McManus/1991](#) 93-94[McManus/1991](#) 93-94[McManus/1991](#) 93-94**Notes****Orientation:** vertical up along down.**Position:** inc ; aris ; inc ; undecorated**Incision:** punched

Macalister/1945, 84: 'bold scores, punched and rubbed'.

Date: 366 - 483 (McManus/1991)

McManus/1991, 93-94.

Goidelic (ogham)

Ling. Notes: See McManus/1991, 108, 116.**Palaeography:** none**Legibility:** same

Macalister/1945, 84: 'a little chipped, so that some of the vowels are lost, but of the reading there can be no doubt. The notches of the I in the first word are accidentally grouped so as to make AUA, but the engraver's intention cannot be questioned. Preceding the initial C there are some scratches, apparently modern, but in any case of no significance'.

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: After 55, all in all seven vowel notches are recognizable. There are hardly any traces visible of Macalister's 1A and 2A. Although the two Ls in CALLITI seem to be well separated, we might think of reading CASITI instead.

Lines: 1**Carving** 0**errors:** 0**Doubtful:** no**Names**• [C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]S](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)• [C\[A\]S](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)• [McManus/1991](#), 111: CALLITI Goidelic? Also see p. 112, and 180 note 57.**References**• [Gippert/Web](#) Ogham 81 photo, drawing substantial discussion [[Gippert 81](#)]• [Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 photo, drawing concise discussion• [Zieglert/1981](#) 145-146, 258 concise discussion

Ogham Stone as CIIC 81 and CISP GARES/1

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for ...
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
?item rdfs:label ?label .
?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
?item oghamonto:within ?c .
?c a oghamonto:County .
?c rdfs:label ?county .
?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df = df.via(https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/n40kg-ogham-sites-maps)
```


	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062					
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168					

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()

# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

N40 KG

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	Archaeological Site	→ 0 references
related to	http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529671 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://wikibase.semantic-kompaakt.de/entity/Q1247 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://database.bartnrd.de/entity/Q1000294 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y00000081 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level High

certainty description on-site survey at exhibition area

method used on-site survey

acting person Florian Thiery

source type (detail) on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic) on-site survey (source type)

method description on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision ±0.0001°

location type Exhibition Site

point type Exhibition

→ 0 references

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level

certainty description

Low

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurrans (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurrans" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurrans. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17."

method used

acting person

source type (generic)

source type (detail)

method description

precision

location type

point type

Georeferencing

Florian Thiery

Textual Description

Paper

found in old documents

±0.0001°

Findspot

Location of a Place as a Concept

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q804647.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en." }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split(","))
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label='ogham sites')
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    # Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix legend
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
    colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
    county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

    patches = []
    for county, color in county_colors.items():
        county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
        county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
        patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
    plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
    plt.show()

    # Map 3: Density map with normalized values
    x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
    y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

    # Calculate kernel density
    xy = np.vstack([x, y])
    kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
    density = kde(xy)

    # Normalize density to range [0, 1]
    density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
    gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
    plt.show()
```


	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows x 8 columns

via <https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

Wikidata

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Neatly
- Help
- Donate
- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concise URL
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Q130529871 edit

→ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	CIC 81
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

Instance of

- ogham stone edit → 0 references + add reference
- Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit → 0 references + add reference
- archaeological artifact edit → 0 references

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294 → 0 references

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148---- → 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392 → 0 references

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

edit

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of	Media item	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

license	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

has technique	Photogrammetry	edit
---------------	-----------------------------	-------------------

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)Editor: [Florian Thierj](#)Contact Person: [Florian Thierj](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)
Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

CnFdI
3D DATA ENRICHMENT

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item

Semantic Kompakkt [Q1247]

Main page
Query service
Sample queries
Advanced text search
Recent changes

Browse
FactGrid Viewer
Knowledge Browser
EntiTree genealogies

Project Spaces
Blog
Projects historically
Projects alphabetically
Projects personally
To Do
SPARQL Lab

Items & Properties
New Item
MergeItems
Batch fragments
QuickStatements
Directory of Properties
New Property
Data modeling
Help

Lexemes

New Lexeme
Search

Tools

What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

↕ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of	Ogham Stone	↕ 0 references
Research projects that contributed to this data set	The FactGrid Ogham Project (2024-)	↕ 0 references
Language	Ogham	↕ 0 references
Genre classification	Ogham Stone	↕ 0 references
Script style	Ogham	↕ 0 references

inscription	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCCI CALLITI	↕ 0 references
Persons mentioned	cassittas	↕ 0 references
	Calliti	↕ 0 references
Things mentioned	MAQI	↕ 0 references
	MUCCI	↕ 0 references
	MUCCI	↕ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son

MAQ | MAC | /-#- | MACCI | MAQI | MACV | MACI

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-#- MACCI MAQI MACV MACI

MUCCI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe

/-#- | MACCU | MOCU | MOCCI | MOCO

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCCI	túath, tribe	/-#- MACCU MOCU MOCCI MOCO

overpass turbo

```

1 /*
2 This is an example Overpass query.
3 Try it out by pressing the Run button above!
4 You can find more examples with the Load tool.
5 */
6 node
7   [historic=ogham_stone]
8   {{{bbox}}};
9 out;

```

```

<node id="5145413640" lat="52.1102476" lon="-10.4731913">
  <tag k="historic" v="ogham_stone"/>
  <tag k="inscription" v="ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA"/>
  <tag k="moved" v="no"/>
  <tag k="name" v="CIIC 178"/>
  <tag k="project" v="ogham.link"/>
  <tag k="ref:IE:smr" v="KE052-059002-"/>
  <tag k="source" v="survey"/>
  <tag k="wikidata" v="Q70892682"/>
  <tag k="wikimedia_commons" v="File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg"/>
</node>

```

Node 5145413640

Tags

- historic = ogham_stone
- inscription = ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
- moved = no
- name = CIIC 178
- project = ogham.link
- ref:IE:smr = KE052-059002-
- source = survey
- wikidata = Q70892682
- wikimedia_commons = File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

Coordinates:
52.1102476 / -10.4731913 (latlon)

geladen – Nodes: 7, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 7, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
geladen – Nodes: 106, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 106, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

via <https://overpass-turbo.eu/s/1lwq>

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

OpenStreetMap [Overpass-Turbo]

THX to
Lozana !!!

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* to get the 3D file view location & *Wikidata* to get all external IDs

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper ×

+ Filter

object of representation 🗑️

+ Show

file view 🗑️

wikidata id 🗑️

Limit

[Query source](#)

```
1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21
```

1 result in 513 ms </> Code

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e542110da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* (as starting point), *Wikidata* (to get external IDs), *FactGrid* (to get Fuzzy-SL ID), and *Fuzzy Spatial Locations* (*fuzzy-sl*) to get coordinates*

*NB: Not possible out of the box – requires additional config of the allowlist & relatively complex syntax, prone to mistakes when writing manually

[Query source](#)

THX to Lozana !!!

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id
10 ?Factgrid_id ?fuzzy_id ?coordinates WHERE {
11 SERVICE wikibase:label {
12 bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
13 VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
14 ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
15 ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
16 ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
17
18 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
19
20 SERVICE wdqs: {
21 ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
22 wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
23 wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
24 wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
25 }
26
27 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fg:), ?Factgrid_id)) AS ?Factgrid_item)
28 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
29 ?Factgrid_item fgt:P1215 ?fuzzy_id.
30 }
31
32 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fslwd:), ?fuzzy_id)) AS ?fuzzy_item)
33 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> {
34 ?fuzzy_item fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates.
35 }
36 }
37

```

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id	fuzzy_id	coordinates
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148---	<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>	Q1000294	Q74	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)

Holy Wells

Wikidata / OSM / FDO

Table - 25 Ergebnisse in 1876 ms Code Herunter

item	ItemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed
Q:121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well		Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcd3a3204744a33b2255465028b8>
Q:126448724	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.4730101 52.7209032)	8517818852	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/clomanagh-lobermurry-02f47554c604a8b8665ea1bc009fd5>
Q:126649228	Lacken Well		Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5beb9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582>
Q:126487120	St Coleman's Well		Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinson-st-colmans-well-low-poly-f6e498530c648ae73cfd09663954a0>
Q:122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well		Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f79e64b434a6ea08676229b493d>
Q:122304309	Saint Molin's Well (Mullennakill)		Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfff49b2f3d4348d5cade4f869ad33>
Q:126456441	Columbkille's Well		Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40cfa4f0437c98ac7f5>
Q:126454844	Lady's Well		Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bcf22e184897a5b8e758cf7249e>
Q:114439798	Kenny's Well		Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e22263342cfc3>
Q:126458702	St. Nicholas's Well (Killamery)		Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae58dff8da>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9888a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival 2		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9888a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:129263926	Holy Well		Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-jeipoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec40c7430ccbf448869>
Q:126374490	Trinity Well		Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3cd851>
Q:122302608	St. Kieran's Well		Point(-7.3800887 52.3975027)	10544065862	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/whitechurch-kilkieran-st-kierans-well-8cdea3b21314058eb7b69faca418d76>
Q:121840779	St. Lachtain's Well		Point(-7.38951 52.7316)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14daa74d33bb076407134e81e>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122189562	Saint Augustine's Well		Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fda14a189a1a59d2e123b1e4>
Q:126456468	Holy Cross well		Point(-7.0437511 52.4878257)	8513475323	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilcross-holy-cross-well-low-poly-ca165580c28429392b1a06491333148>
Q:126657210	St. David's Well		Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144739129	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2ae79bb6ab7c69a8>
Q:126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well		Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8a3147ecb29f367>
Q:126487358	St Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3565632 52.6115585)	8517798092	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/toberbreedia-st-brigids-well-56e71b0735fc4f17bdf3e4c5b2a12a7>
Q:126454422	St Leonard's Well		Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690>

Holy Wells having Sketchfab Links to 3D-Models

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/pq67u>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Sheestown Townland: St Fiachra's Well

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

St. Lachtain's Well (qualifier)

Label: No label defined
 Description: No description defined
 Also known as: No label defined

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	St. Lachtain's Well	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Táin Lachtain St. Lachtain's Well Tairnaghagh Tairnaghain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Basenian	No label defined	No description defined	

All referenced languages

E26

Statements

- Holy Well **Saint Lachtain's Well**
 - + 0 references
- Spring
 - + 3 references
- Holy well
 - date of use: abandoned 1830
 - + 2 references
- architectural structure
 - + 0 references

Image

Tairnaghagh - Tain Lachtain-02.jpg
 3,000 × 2,000 (3.54 MB)
 + 0 references

significant person

- William Kinvela
 - + 1 reference

named after

- Lachtain mac Taitin
 - + 0 references

country

- Ireland
 - + 0 references

located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny
 - + 0 references
- Freshford
 - + 0 references

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK013-025----

+ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap way ID

935503837

+ 0 references

Wiki Loves Monuments ID

IE-KK-0248

+ 0 references

OpenStreetMap

Way: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)

Version #8

ref:Esri requires heritage=2
 Edited 11 months ago by geonovig
 Changed 411015336

Tags

alt_name	Tobertschtain
amenity	place_of_worship
class_date	0133-06-23
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walked enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subcircular water basin which is covered in water tanks.
heritage	2
heritageoperator	IEswr
name	Tobertschtain
name_en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name_etymology_wiki	Q11674003
id	
name_ru	Тобертштайн
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:Esri	K0013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey
surveydate	2021-05-26
uploadetf:tab	https://sfrs.ly/0wVb
water	spring
wikidata	Q121840779
wikimedia_commons	Category:Tobertschtain

Nodes

- + 11 nodes

Download XML

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

Govan Stones

Semantic Kompakkt / FDO

6.2 Govan 2

The hogbacks of Govan have been the subject of intense study since James Lang's original consideration of the Scottish hogbacks (1974); scholarly interest in this monument type has only increased since (Lang 1984; Lang 1994; Ritchie 2004; Crawford 2005; Williams 2015; Whitworth 2016; Barnes 2019). Govan 2 (Lang 1, ECMS 2), is one of the best preserved of the Govan hogbacks. A band of a variety of median-incised motifs has been carved along the bottom of the monument; while the art historical similarities with the Irish sea and Cumbria have been considered in previous discussion of these motifs (Lang 1994, 125), but it is also worth noting that the ring-chain utilised in the band is very similar to that found elsewhere in the Govan collection on Govan 24 (see Section 6.16 below). Above this band, two rows of concave tiles have been carved on each side. A small panel survives on one of the short edges of the monument, which has been decorated with a swastika motif. Two small panels of step pattern flank this panel. Two weathered beast heads remain, one on each short face of the monument. The ridge of Govan 2, however, is significantly worn. The digital three-dimensional model of the stone revealed that at least one side of the ridge had been previously decorated with step pattern, which has not been commented on previously (Figure 6.2). The identification of this pattern has recently been confirmed by John Borland, who has been illustrating the corpus of Govan monuments.

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Figure 6.2. Faint remnants of step pattern can be seen on the ridge of Govan 2, above the uppermost row of tile-pattern.

Kasten, Megan Nichole. 2019. 'The Govan Stones Revealed: Digital Imaging in the Analysis of Early Medieval Sculpture'. Doctoral Thesis (PhD), University of Glasgow. <https://doi.org/10.5525/gla.thesis.74266>.

E22

E25

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Govan Old Parish Church, Glasgow, Scotland

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

[Related agents](#)

[Creation](#)

[External Links](#)

[Related object structure](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ **Semantic Kompakkt**

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

- Wikibase
- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone o2 (Hogback) (Q1772)

Archaeological Artifact

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone O2 (Hogback)	Archaeological Artifact

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of Human-Made Object

▼ 0 references

Wikidata id Q136659904

▼ 0 references

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki
- Wikibase
- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

E22

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone o2 (Hogback) (Q1773)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks

▼ In more languages
Continue

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone O2 (Hogback)	Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of Media item

▼ 0 references

license Creative Commons Attribution

▼ 0 references

method Photogrammetry

▼ 0 references

software Agisoft Metashape

▼ 0 references

ZBrush

▼ 0 references

object of representation Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

▼ 0 references

file view <https://semantic-kompakt.de/entity/6900db0bab8796a7fba84f05>

▼ 0 references

external link <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>

▼ 0 references

right held by Megan Nichole Kasten

▼ 0 references

contact person Florian Thieri

▼ 0 references

created by (event) Creation

carried out by Megan Nichole Kasten

▼ 0 references

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Semantic Kompakt Wikibase

Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item)

Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow

Related agents

Rightsowner: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Creator: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Contact Person: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI.engine](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ **Semantic Kompakkt** (made with KIRI Engine)

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase

- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

Tools

- What links here
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- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
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- Concept URI

Item Discussion

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q1772)

Archaeological Artifact

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)	Archaeological Artifact

Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of	Human-Made Object	E22
		0 references

Wikidata id	Q136659904
	0 references

- Main page
- Recent changes
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Wikibase

- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Upload file
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- List URI

Item Discussion

Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item) (Q1775)

Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item)	Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of	Media item
	0 references

license	Creative Commons Attribution
	0 references

method	Photogrammetry
--------	----------------

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase

Govan Stone 2 ★

WissKI

Object Name
Govan Stone 2

Authored on
Mon, 3 Nov 2025 - 11:01

ID set
[Wikidata \(Q136659904\)](#)

Type
[hogback](#)

Subject	Predicate	Object	Graph	Adapter
In-coming triples				
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/wisski/navigate/1/view	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#sameAs	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/originatesFrom	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
Out-going triples				
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E22_Human-Made_Object	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#sameAs	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/wisski/navigate/1/view	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/originatesFrom	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P2_has_type	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088c7951402	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	https://www.ontscidoc3d.hs-mainz.de/OntPreHer3D/R42_has_3D_preview_in	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088d4147ace	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P1_is_identified_by	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P1_is_identified_by	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088bbe211a6	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter
https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/69088b8ed699d	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/eid	"1"^^xsd:integer	https://chnt-1.wisski.cloud/baseFields	Default WissKI Distillery Adapter

Govan Stone 2 @ WissKI Cloud (with CIDOC CRM backbone)

Campanian Ignimbrite

fuzzy-sl Wikibase (wikibase.cloud)

About 40'000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Findspots with ***spatial-type: Cave*** and ***Archaeological Site***

fuzzy-s1 RDF Modelling Scheme

fuzzy-sl Wikibase Modelling Scheme

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Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/1221172611>

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historic	archaeological_site
name:en	Franchthi Cave
wikidata	Q1441331
wikipedia	en:Franchthi Cave

Franchthi Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

Franchthi Cave (Greece) ^{EN}

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45

The Franchthi Cave (Greece) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsi:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsi:certaintyLevel)	high (fsi:high) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsi:hasReference)	Fedele et al., 2003 (xsd:string)
<code>partOf</code> (fsi:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsi:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
<code>siteType</code> (fsi:siteType)	archaeologicalSite (fsi:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsi:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsi:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsi:Cave) [x]
<code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_45_geom (fsi:cisite_45_geom)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (placides:Place) [x] Site (fsi:Site) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>closeMatch</code> (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 122172811 (122172811) [x] Q1444331 (wikidata:Q1444331) [x]
<code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>scopeNote</code> (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>is member of</code> (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances collection (fsi:Entity_collection) Place instances collection (fsi:Place_collection) Site instances collection (fsi:Site_collection)
<code>is used by</code> (prov:used) of	cisite_45_activity (fsi:cisite_45_activity)

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Further languages: Add links

Item Discussion

Franchthi Cave (Q111)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Franchthi Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site Archaeological Site
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2003
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology Geology
has coordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 37°29′21.47″N 23°7′52.07″E certainty level: High findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap method used: Geoparsing writing person: Foma Schenk instance type (literal): Textual Description source type (literal): Paper method description: CI findspot related from literature precision: ±0.0001° location type: Findspot point type: NotLuzr Place 1 reference
WKT Geometry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point(37.131 37.422) 0 references

Franchthi Cave in the LOD Cloud

via trentu.ca

Roland Sore, via flickr rolabin/30105173063

Fig. 14.9. Examples of cutmarks observed on specimens taxa other than ungulates at Crvena Stijena: a) mammoth mandible (M5); b) horse distal tibia (M1); c) *Ursus* sp. metapodial fragment (XXIV); d) *Ursus* sp. fifth metacarpal fragment (M1).

via <http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/10879170567>

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archaeological_site	megalith
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	neolithic
name	Crvena stijena
name:en	Red wall
wikidata	Q121418883
wikipedia	https://bs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crvena_stijena_(Crna_Gora)

Crvena Stiljena Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) ^{EN}

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_51

The Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: [Go](#) **Download Options:** Format: [Turtle \(TTL\)](#) [Download](#)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scope:note:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	high (fsl:high) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	Morley & Woodward, 2011 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_51_geom (fsl:cisite_51_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (fsl:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1087917057 (1087917057) [x] Q121418883 (wikidata:Q121418883) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
is member of (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place instances collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site instances collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_51_activity (fsl:cisite_51_activity)

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Item Discussion

Crvena Stijena Cave (Q89)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

+ in more languages

Compare

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Crvena Stijena Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site 0 references Archaeological Site 0 references
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots 0 references
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave 0 references
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology 0 references Geology 0 references
has coordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 42°46′44.4″N, 18°28′53.4″E certainty level: High certainty description: findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap method used: Georeferencing action person: Floris Schenk source type (rank): Textual Description source law (label): Paper method description: CI findspot related from literature precision: ±0.0001° location type: Findspot point type: Natural Place + 1 reference
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Morley & Woodward, 2011 0 references

Crvena Stijena Cave in the LOD Cloud

via <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102912> © Tzanova et al.

via <http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11109379095>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

ele	300
name	Toplitsa Cave
natural	cave_entrance
source_ref	10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102912
wikidata	Q61788595

Toplitsa Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

To conclude ...

... and open for discussion ...

- 1 **Methodologically:** Semantic integration transforms heterogeneous cultural heritage data into interoperable, FAIR Knowledge Graphs.
- 2 **Scientifically:** Federated Knowledge Graphs reveal new connections across cultural, textual, and environmental domains.
- 3 **Strategically:** Sustainable, FAIR-aligned infrastructures depend on continuous, community-driven curation and semantic enrichment.

Finis!

Thx!

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